

Men's Understanding of Natal Health Issues and Their Role in Maternal Care

Saravanan. R
Ph.D., Research Scholar
Department of Population Studies
Annamalai University

Received: Jan 27, 2026

Accepted: Feb 22, 2026

Published: Feb 24, 2026

Abstract

Male involvement in maternal health is widely recognized as pivotal for improving pregnancy outcomes and advancing gender equity. However, research specific to men's knowledge and participation in natal health, especially within rural Indian contexts, remains limited. This study assesses the extent of men's knowledge regarding natal health issues and explores socio-demographic factors influencing their awareness in Chidambaram Taluk, Cuddalore district, Tamil Nadu—a region selected due to its lower Human Development and Gender Inequality indices. A cross-sectional study of married young men with one child born six months before proceeding the survey at under privileged district of Tamil Nadu in 2023. Totally 259 young men participated in the survey. While the majority of respondents demonstrated awareness of natal health problems, significant differences emerged based on educational attainment and place of residence. Urban men and those with higher secondary education or a degree exhibited substantially greater knowledge. Logistic regression indicated that the urban advantage in knowledge diminished when educational attainment was included, emphasizing education as the primary determinant. Education is the most influential factor in men's knowledge of natal health issues, overshadowing the urban-rural divide. Targeted education-based interventions are crucial, especially for rural and less-educated populations, to enhance men's engagement in maternal health and ultimately improve maternal and child health outcomes.

Key Words: Male Involvement, Maternal Health, Natal Knowledge, Educational Attainment

Introduction

Male involvement in childcare is one of the most important issues in reproductive and child health programmes in both developed and developing countries. It involves men being present, accessible, available, understanding, and eager to learn about the pregnancy process, providing emotional, physical, and financial support to the expectant woman. However, studies have shown that male involvement in maternal and child health (MCH) care is limited in various regions (Narang, H., & Singhal, S. 2016). (Narang, H., & Singhal, S. (2016). Men as partners in maternal health: An analysis of male awareness and attitude. *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 2(3), 388–392). Similarly, in Indian societies, childbirth and childcare have traditionally been perceived as women's responsibilities, despite efforts to

emphasize the importance of male partners' involvement. Recognizing the significance of male behaviour and perceptions in MCH care, national programmes have attempted to encourage male involvement. Considerable progress in reducing maternal and infant mortality rates, largely due to the availability and accessibility of MCH services, male awareness and involvement remain essential to take of ante natal neo natal and post natal care.

The 1994 International Conference on Population and Development (ICPD), held in Cairo, recommended males to be involved in the reproductive health of their wives or partners. It also encouraged reproductive health care programmers to adopt a more holistic approach that includes men and focuses on couples rather than focusing on women alone.

The practice of male involvement in MCH services also facilitates their contact with the health care system and represents an opportunity to acquire healthcare services and health promotion for their benefit. This includes encouraging women to be aware, access, and seek the necessary health care needs, followed by the adoption of appropriate family planning methods. Notably, their involvement in maternal health-care services also makes them aware of the high risk in pregnancy, obstetric danger signs, feeding practices for infants, and immunization of the child, significantly improving the maternal health indicators

The participation of men in the broader perspective of safe motherhood and childhood was found to be inadequate in few developing countries. In India, despite gains in MCH, according to National Family Health Survey-4 report, male involvement in MCH care is still low (International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS) and ICF. 2017. National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4), India, 2015-16: [State Name]. Mumbai: IIPS). In addition, there is a dearth in the literature in India and other developing countries about the male partner's involvement in all aspects of MCH care. Hence the current review was planned to discuss and provide a clear picture of the contribution of male involvement in MCH care, the factors determining it and address the feasible strategies to improve it.

Reviews

Maternal health and positive pregnancy outcomes are fundamental for the well-being of families and societies. Traditionally, men have often been on the periphery of their partners' reproductive health care, there is an increasing understanding of their pivotal role in family decision-making, which significantly affects pregnancy outcomes (Mohammed et al., 2019; Yargawa & Leonardi-Bee, 2015).

Recognizing that male partners are crucial key players, their involvement in maternal health is now considered essential for improving the health of women, newborns, and families (Daniele, 2021, Galle et al., 2021).

This introduction will explore the multifaceted roles of male partners in ensuring maternal health and fostering positive pregnancy experiences, drawing upon current research and perspectives that highlight their support and influence on healthcare utilization and pregnancy outcomes (Daniele, 2021, Galle et al., 2021).

Increased male involvement is not only beneficial for maternal and child health but is also viewed as a marker of gender equity and a crucial social determinant of health. Male partner involvement in maternal health is a multi-concept that includes a man's engagement, interest, and participation in the process and experience of pregnancy, childbirth, and new parenthood (Daniele, 2021).

This consist discussing maternal health issues with one's spouse, making joint decisions about pregnancy spacing and the utilization of maternal services, accompanying their partners to antenatal care in health facilities, providing social, emotional, physical, and financial support (Mohammed et al., 2019, Unawari et al., 2023, Wai et al., 2015), and relieving their pregnant partners from performing heavy workloads (Mohammed et al., 2019). It signifies men being "present, accessible, available, understanding, willing to learn about the pregnancy process and eager to provide emotional, physical and financial support to the woman carrying the child" (Mohammed et al., 2019).

The benefits of male involvement in maternal healthcare are numerous. These include better utilization of ANC and postnatal care services, more hospital deliveries, and a greater likelihood of skilled birth attendance at the time of delivery (Yargawa & Leonardi-Bee, 2015, Tokhi et al., 2018 *as cited in Model 16.pdf*). The presence and support of a male partner during labour are linked to a shorter labour duration and a decreased need for painkillers (Srivastava et al., 2015 *as cited in 17.pdf*).

Studies have also indicated that increased partner support can assist in reducing depressive symptoms in postpartum women (Yargawa & Leonardi-Bee, 2015, Dennis & Ross, 2006, Gremigni et al., 2011 *as cited in 2.pdf*).

Male partners significantly influence a woman's access to and utilization of essential maternal health services. For instance, women whose male partners take time to understand what happens during ANC visits are more likely to attend their first ANC visit within the first trimester of pregnancy and have skilled delivery attendants at birth (Mohammed et al., 2019). Encouraging the first antenatal consultation as a "couples visit" can ensure that male partners receive vital information about pregnancy health and birth preparedness as early as feasible in the pregnancy (*Reference*). Male involvement is also linked to a greater likelihood of women delivering at health facilities and being attended by skilled birth attendants (Mangeni et al., 2012, Nyandieka et al., 2016 *as cited in 18.pdf*). Moreover, male partner involvement contributes to improved utilization of PNC services for both mothers and newborns (Mohammed et al., 2019). In the context of prevention of mother-to-child transmission of HIV, male involvement, particularly couple counselling and HIV testing, is associated with decreased infant HIV infection rates and increased HIV-free survival (Aluisio et al., 2011; Byamugisha et al., 2010 *as cited in 18.pdf*).

International bodies like the World Health Organization (WHO) emphasize the active involvement of men during pregnancy, delivery, and the postpartum period as an effective method to improve the health outcomes of mothers and their newborn babies (WHO, 2015 as

cited in 17.pdf]. However, the WHO stresses that men's participation should guarantee that women's autonomy in decision-making is respected. Despite the acknowledged importance, male involvement in maternal health remains a challenge in many low- and middle-income countries (Aborigo et al., 2018).

Despite the growing recognition of the importance of male involvement in ensuring maternal health and positive pregnancy outcomes, several research gaps persist in this field. Yargawa and Leonardi-Bee, 2015 highlighted a general dearth of evidence specifically assessing the effect of male involvement on distinct maternal health outcomes within developing countries, advocating for further high-quality studies in this area. Chattopadhyay and Govil, 2020 also noted gaps in the literature concerning men's roles in maternal care, especially within the context of India. Furthermore, they pointed out that many prior studies have adopted predominantly "problem-oriented approaches to avoiding maternal death" rather than exploring the broader spectrum of male involvement (Chattopadhyay & Govil, 2020). A significant research gap identified by Galle et al. 2021 is the lack of a universally standardised and multidimensional index for assessing male involvement in maternal health. Galle et al.'s (2021) systematic review aimed to examine the conceptualization of male involvement in maternal health within quantitative literature, indicating an existing gap in the clarity and standardization of this concept within research methodologies.

In this regard the study aims to assess the extent of knowledge about natal health issues and to find the factors influence the ability to attain comprehensive knowledge of these health concern among men in Chidambaram Taluk of Cuddalore district, Tamil Nadu. Chidambaram is one of the important areas consists more number of villages around it.

Material and Methods

A cross-sectional study design was used to assess the husband's knowledge regarding natal health issues if their wife's in Chidambaram taluk.

Cuddalore district has been chosen since it was ranked the bottom ten districts with respect to Human Development Index and Gender Inequality Index. Cuddalore district has divided with 13 medical blocks by the Directorate of Public Health, Tamil Nadu namely Annagramam, Cuddalore, Panruti, Kurinjipadi, Parangipettai, Sivakkam, Nallur, Kattumanrkoil, Keerapalayam, Krishnapuram, Kammapuram, Mangalampet, and Mangalore.

Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted to conduct the study. Out of the 13 medical blocks, two medical blocks are located in the Chidambaram taluk namely Sivakkam block and Parangipettai block In Sivkkam block totally six PHCs are functioning and in Parangipettai block, 5 PHCs are providing health services. The selected PHCs are Chidambaram UPHC and Komaratchi PHC from Sivakkam medical block and Gavaraipattu and B. Muttular from Parangipattai medical block. Totally 23 villages and four urban wards were selected as study settings. A total of 361 households were identified and solicited their consent to participate in the survey. Approached all the 361 households in their respective locations only 259 households' men were cooperated to complete the interview

The study was conducted a household should have at least one young married couple with at least one child within six months preceding the survey and men should be married in the ages of 20-39 as a basic characteristics. . Chi square test was employed to assess the association between categorical variables. Logistic regression analysis was used to correlate demographics with knowledge level of men regarding natal health issues

Result

The knowledge of natal problems among men of their partners, the highest proportion was found to be high with excessive bleeding followed by high blood pressure etc., From the responses, it is understandable that majority of males are knowledgeable on the natal health problems of their partners, which is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Men's Knowledge Regarding Natal Problems their Partners

Among the various natal problems, compared to other symptoms respondents are less knowledgeable in Breech presentation.

Knowledge level of men

The respondents had known all the problems of women considered as complete knowledge and if the respondents had knowledge on either one or two problems considered as less knowledge. Around 79 percent almost three fourth of the respondents had complete knowledge on women's issues but one fourth not having awareness.

Figure 2. Men's Level of Knowledge on Natal Problems of their partners

Knowledge Level of Men based on Socio-Economic and Demographic Variables

Understanding men's knowledge of their partners' natal health issues is important in and child health outcomes. Table 1 shows the level of knowledge among men have regarding natal problems and how it varies based on socio-economic and demographic (SED) factors

Table 1. Men's Knowledge Regarding Natal Problems of Their Partners by Socio-Economic and Demographic (SED) Variables

SED Variables	Knowledge Index on Natal Problems	
	Less Knowledge	Complete Knowledge
Age of the Respondent ^{NS}		
Below 30 years	30.3	69.7
30-34 years	21.9	78.1
35 and above years	37.5	62.5
Place of Residence *		
Rural	34.4	65.6
Urban	20.6	79.4
Religion ^{NS}		
Hindu	29.2	70.8
Others	27.5	72.2
Caste ^{NS}		
SC/ST	33.6	66.4
MBC	24.4	75.6
Others	27.0	73.0
Educational Attainment ***		
Up to Middle	63.0	37.0
Higher	48.9	51.1
Higher Secondary	19.4	80.6
Any Degree	18.8	81.2
Occupation ^{NS}		
Agriculture	36.3	63.7
Non-Agriculture	23.3	76.7

Age at Marriage ^{NS}		
Below 27 years	37.1	62.9
27-30 years	24.8	75.2
30 and above years	29.4	70.6
Family Type ^{NS}		
Nuclear	28.2	71.8
Joint	34.4	65.6

NS- Not Significance, ***, * p Value is <0.05 and 0.000 respectively

A significant difference is observed between rural and urban respondents. Urban men (79.4%) exhibit higher knowledge levels than their rural counterparts (65.6%), indicating a possible urban advantage in access to health information. Education is an important factor determining of knowledge level of men. Men with only middle-level education (37.0%) have the lowest knowledge levels, while those with a higher secondary education (80.6%) and a degree (81.2%) have the highest awareness. The findings indicate that education and place of residence are the most influential factors in determining men's knowledge of natal problems of their partners. Higher educational attainment significantly improves awareness and Urban men demonstrate higher knowledge levels, indicates better access to healthcare information in urban settings and in educated men. While other socio-economic factors such as caste, occupation, and age at marriage do not show strong associations.

This logistic regression analysis shown in table 2 identify key determinants affecting men's awareness of natal problems of their partners. The models consider socio-economic factors such as place of residence and education to examine their impact on knowledge levels. By assessing the statistical significance and odds ratios (Exp(B)), this analysis aims to identify the most influential factors that contribute to variations in men's knowledge.

Table 2 Determinants of Men's Knowledge Regarding Natal Problems: Logistic Regression Analysis

Model	Variables	Sig.	Exp(B)	
Model 1	Place of Residence	Rural®		
		Urban	0.018	2.022
Model 2	Place of Residence	Rural®		
		Urban	0.403	1.314
	Education	Up to Middle®		
		High School	0.237	1.794
		Higher Secondary	0.001	6.707
Any Degree	0.000	6.771		

The logistic regression results are presented in two models. Model 1 showing the effect of Place of Residence on knowledge level and Model 2 present the Effect of Place of Residence and Education together. model 1 indicate that, the odds ratio for urban residence is 2.022 with a significance level of 0.018, indicating that men living in urban areas are twice as likely to have better knowledge of natal problems compared to those in rural areas. The significant p-value shows that place of residence has a significant effect on knowledge levels in Model 1. When

education is included as an additional variable in Model 2, the effect of place of residence (urban) becomes insignificant ($p = 0.403$, $\text{Exp}(B) = 1.314$), indicate that the previously observed urban advantage may be explained by differences in educational attainment. the model 2 explains Men with a higher secondary education are 6.707 times more likely to have complete knowledge compared to those with only middle-level education ($p = 0.001$). Those with any degree have an even stronger effect, being 6.771 times more likely to possess knowledge ($p = 0.000$). Hence the results indicate that Education plays a unavoidable role in determining men's knowledge of natal problems among their partners. The strong and highly significant effects of higher secondary and degree-level education indicate that better-educated men are far more likely to be aware of their partners' maternal health issues. The influence of urban residence diminishes when education is accounted for, which indicate that the urban advantage is largely due to higher educational attainment rather than urban living itself. Based on the finding the study suggest that the need for education-based interventions to improve men's awareness of maternal health, particularly in lower-educated and rural populations.

Discussion on Findings

While women are the direct recipients of maternal healthcare services the involvement and awareness of their male partners are equally important. However the present studies reveal a persistent knowledge gap (29 %) among men regarding natal health issues. One significant factor contributing to this gap is the influence of traditional gender roles (Narang, H., & Singhal, S. (2016). Men as partners in maternal health: an analysis of male awareness and attitude. *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 2(3), 388–392. Retrieved from <https://www.ijrcog.org/index.php/ijrcog/article/view/114>). In the context of reproductive and natal health these roles often cast women as the primary caregivers and recipients of health services (Fotso, J.C., Higgins-Steele, A. & Mohanty, S. Male engagement as a strategy to improve utilization and community-based delivery of maternal, newborn and child health services: evidence from an intervention in Odisha, India. *BMC Health Serv Res* 15 (Suppl 1), S5 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-15-S1-S5>) while men are relegated to the role of economic providers and decision-makers and without direct engagement in health-related matters. These societal constructs discourage men from actively participating in conversations or decisions concerning maternal health. The pregnancy and childbirth are considered exclusively "women's matters," (Kaushal P, Khapre M, Das A, Kumari R, Sharma M. Community Perspective of Male Involvement in Maternal Health Care in Uttarakhand, India: A Qualitative Study. *J Obstet Gynaecol India*. 2023 Apr;73(2):113-122. doi: 10.1007/s13224-022-01672-5. Epub 2022 Sep 10. PMID: 37073237; PMCID: PMC10105805) and male involvement is viewed as unnecessary. As a result, men may feel discomfort in seeking information regarding the maternal health of their partners. The exclusion of men from pregnancy matters significantly contributes to the persistent knowledge gap among men regarding natal health and it is shaped by entrenched social norms healthcare system limitations and attitudes. The cultural taboos act as silent barriers that prevent men from accessing, discussing and engaging with the maternal health of their partners. In many societies, topics related to pregnancy, menstruation, childbirth, and female anatomy are deemed sensitive, and shameful particularly in patriarchal cultures. In such environments men are discouraged from participating in the pregnancy matters. Women do not openly share details about their pregnancy with male family members or even their own partners, (Aborigo, R.A., Reidpath, D.D., Oduro, A.R. *et al.* Male involvement in maternal health: perspectives of opinion leaders. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* 18, 3 (2018).

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-017-1641-9>) fearing stigma or breach of tradition. Clinics and hospitals often cater exclusively to women for antenatal and reproductive services, creating environments where men feel unwelcome. Another most important contributors to the deficiency is the limited provision of comprehensive sex and health education for men. Without foundational knowledge about reproductive health men are less likely to engage meaningfully in pregnancy-related care and thereby perpetuating a significant knowledge gap in natal health. School curricula avoid detailed discussions on reproductive health. Sex education is gender-biased, focusing more on women's reproductive roles and neglecting the involvement of men. Men are excluded from community-based maternal health education programs, which are mostly targeted at women. Lack of involvement in antenatal care, many men are accompany their partners to antenatal visits, as a result they miss opportunities to receive information's from healthcare providers.

Among men the level of formal education significantly influences the knowledge level about their partners' natal health problems. Men with higher levels of education are more likely to recognize the signs and symptoms of natal complications and support their partners in seeking healthcare services (Jungari S, Paswan B. What he knows about her and how it affects her? Husband's knowledge of pregnancy complications and maternal health care utilization among tribal population in Maharashtra, India. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*. 2019 Feb 13;19(1):70. doi: 10.1186/s12884-019-2214-x. PMID: 30760234; PMCID: PMC6373054). Misconceptions about pregnancy and childbirth persist due to limited exposure to scientific knowledge, but the educated men are more likely to question cultural taboos that accelerate the male participation in natal care. Men with better education are more likely to communicate openly with their partners about health issues and taking joint decision related to childbirth planning, hospital selection and birth preparedness. Men with formal education are more likely to value institutional delivery over traditional practices and they are very supportive of vaccinations, family planning, and use of maternal healthcare services.

In the present study urban residence initially appears as a strong predictor of better health knowledge. Urban men typically have greater access to healthcare facilities, exposure to information. the present study exhibit that, when education is statistically controlled for the urban effect showing a weak association due to educated individuals regardless of location are more likely to seek health knowledge (Wang W, Zhang Y, Lin B, Mei Y, Ping Z, Zhang Z. The Urban-Rural Disparity in the Status and Risk Factors of Health Literacy: A Cross-Sectional Survey in Central China. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020 May 29;17(11):3848. doi: 10.3390/ijerph17113848. PMID: 32485790; PMCID: PMC7312746). Urban life may bring exposure, but only education transforms that exposure into meaningful understanding. Educated men are more likely to challenge taboos, ask questions, and support their partners regardless of their environment. While urban residence provides physical access to healthcare resources and exposure to information, it is education that equips men with the ability to understand, internalize, and act on natal health knowledge. Once education is accounted for, the place of residence becomes less significant because the real transformation occurs not from where a person lives, but from what they know and how they apply it. Hence, policies aiming to increase male involvement in maternal health must prioritize education over geography to achieve deeper, more sustainable outcomes.

Conclusion

The study reveals a significant knowledge gap among men regarding the natal health of their partners, with approximately 29% lacking adequate awareness. This gap is deeply rooted in a combination of structural, cultural, and educational barriers. Traditional gender roles continue to the notion that pregnancy and childbirth are exclusively women's domains, thereby limiting male participation. The exclusion of men from pregnancy-related conversations, cultural taboos surrounding reproductive health, and the lack of comprehensive sex and health education among men further contribute to their limited understanding. The research also shows that while urban residence initially appears to provide an advantage in the knowledge level but is showing weak association when education is factored. Hence the education is the most significant determinant of men's knowledge about natal health. Educated men, regardless of their location, demonstrate higher levels of health literacy, better communication with their partners, and a greater willingness to engage in maternal health practices.

Suggestions

Based on the findings of the study it is evident that addressing the knowledge gap among men regarding natal health requires an inclusive approach. One of the foremost strategies should be the integration of male-focused reproductive and natal health education into school curricula. Early exposure to such knowledge helps dismantle gender stereotypes and encourages young boys to view maternal health as a shared responsibility. Health systems should actively involve men in antenatal care by encouraging their participation during hospital visits, pregnancy counseling, and childbirth preparation sessions. Training healthcare workers to communicate effectively with male partners and providing male-centric educational materials in local languages can also help bridge the information gap. Media campaigns using social media platforms should be developed to challenge cultural taboos and normalize male involvement in maternal health matters. A policy-level changes are essential to institutionalize male involvement in maternal health under national and state health schemes, with provisions for incentives to couples who participate jointly in natal care.

Reference

- Aborigo, R. A., Reidpath, D. D., Oduro, A. R., & Allotey, P. (2018). Male involvement in maternal health: perspectives of opinion leaders. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 18(1), 3.
- Chattopadhyay, A., & Govil, D. (2020). Men and maternal health care utilization in India and in selected less-developed states: evidence from a large-scale survey 2015–16. *Journal of Biosocial Science*, 53(5), 724–744.
- Daniele, M. A. S. (2021). Male partner participation in maternity care and social support for childbearing women: a discussion paper. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B*, 376(1822), 20200021.
- Galle, A., Griffin, S., Osman, N., Roelens, K., & Degomme, O. (2021). Towards a global framework for assessing male involvement in maternal health: results of an international Delphi study. *BMJ Open*, 11(9), e051361.

- Galle, A., Plaieser, G., Van Steenstraeten, T., Griffin, S., Osman, N. B., Roelens, K., & Degomme, O. (2021). Systematic review of the concept 'male involvement in maternal health' by natural language processing and descriptive analysis. *BMJ Global Health*, 6(4), e004909.
- Mohammed, B. H., Johnston, J. M., Vackova, D., Hassen, S. M., & Yi, H. (2019). The role of male partner in utilization of maternal health care services in Ethiopia: a community-based couple study. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 19(1), 28.
- Tokhi, M., Comrie-Thomson, L., Davis, J., Portela, A., Chersich, M., & Luchters, S. (2018). Involving men to improve maternal and newborn health: a systematic review of the effectiveness of interventions. *PLoS ONE*, 13(1), e0191620.
- Unawari, P. N., Sharma, A., & Verma, A. (2023). Perspectives of Pregnant Women on the Role of Male Partner Involvement in Antenatal Care, Labour and Delivery. *Open Journal of Nursing*, 13(10), 711-722.
- Wai, K. M., Shibanuma, A., Oo, N. N., Fillman, T. J., Saw, Y. M., & Jimba, M. (2015). Are husbands involving in their spouses' utilization of maternal care services?: a cross-sectional study in Yangon, Myanmar. *PLoS ONE*, 10(12), e0144135.
- Yargawa, J., & Leonardi-Bee, J. (2015). Male involvement and maternal health outcomes: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health*, 69(6), 604-612.
- Yargawa, J., & Leonardi-Bee, J. (2015). Male involvement and maternal health outcomes: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health*, 69(6), 604-612.